

A Stratified Early/Middle Holocene Site inside the Qārat al-Kibrīt Dome

Jeffrey I. Rose, Vitaly I. Usik, Diego E. Angelucci and Ali Al-Mahrooqi

ABSTRACT

Qarat al-Kibrīt 1 (QK1) is the first stratified aceramic Neolithic archaeological site excavated in the interior of Oman. The site is situated along the outer rim of the Qarat al-Kibrīt salt dome, an endorheic diapir on the ad-Dakhliyah alluvial plain. QK1 was excavated by the Central Oman Pleistocene Research program during the 2004 field season, yielding three distinct archaeological horizons within approximately one meter of *in situ* Early and Middle Holocene sediments. A single radiometric date was established by AMS measurement on a perforated *Conus* shell recovered from archaeological level 1, while a rough temporal span is estimated for levels 2 and 3 based on the identification of lithic arrowheads belonging to the Neolithic Arabian Bifacial Tradition. Techno-typological analysis of the chipped stone assemblage recovered from the site has documented a variety of lithic reduction strategies employed by the inhabitants of QK1. Given the presence of high quality halite (salt crystal) deposits within the dome that exhibit clear evidence of quarrying activity, we speculate that Neolithic and Bronze Age human groups were drawn to the area in order to exploit this valuable resource as well as the freshwater runoff draining into the endorheic basin.

KEYWORDS: Qarat Al-Kibrīt, Central Oman, Holocene, Lithic, Halite exploitation.

موقع ذو طبقات متراففة يعود إلى بدايات ومنتصف عصر الهولوسين في القبة الملحية بقارة الكبريت

جيفري روز، فيتالي يوسيك، دييجو أنجيلوتشي، علي المحروقي

الملخص

يعدّ موقع قارة الكبريت أول موقع أثري من العصر الحجري الحديث يتم تنقيبُه في داخل عمان. وهو موقع لا يحتوي على فخار، ويوجد على الحافة الخارجية للقبة الملحية بقارة الكبريت الواقعة على سهل المنطقة الداخلية الفيضي. وتعدّ قارة الكبريت حوض تصريف مائي مصمت المسامات ذو شكل مقبب بسبب اندفاع الأملاح من طبقاته السفلية باتجاه الأعلى. تم التنقيب في الموقع في موسم عام ٢٠٠٤م بواسطة « البرنامج البحثي الخاص بعصر البلايستوسين في وسط عمان ». وقد كشف التنقيب عن ثلاثة مستويات أثرية واضحة خلال حوالي متر واحد من ترسبات تعود إلى عصري الهولوسين المبكر والوسيط. تم الحصول على تاريخ إشعاعي مفرد للموقع من خلال فحص قوقعة تم اكتشافها في المستوى الأثري الأول، في حين تم التعرف على فترة زمنية متوقعة للمستويين الثاني والثالث وذلك بناء على رؤوس السهام الحجرية المنتمية لثقافة الأدوات الحجرية ذات الوجهين والتي تتميز بها الجزيرة العربية. وبالنظر إلى وجود ترسبات بلورات الملح عالية الجودة في هذه القبة فإن ذلك يدلل بوضوح على أنه كانت هناك أنشطة لاستخراج الملح. نخمن بأن المجموعات البشرية في العصر الحجري الحديث وفي العصر البرونزي جاءت إلى هذه المنطقة لاستغلال هذا المورد الثمين بالإضافة إلى المياه العذبة التي تجري باتجاه حوض التصريف المصمت.

كلمات مفتاحية: قارة الكبريت، وسط عمان، عصر الهولوسين، الأدوات الحجرية، استغلال الملح.

INTRODUCTION

The archaeological site of Qarat Al-Kibrit 1 (QK1) was discovered in 2004 by the Central Oman Pleistocene Research Project (COPR). The site is situated along the western rim of the Qarat Al-Kibrit salt dome (Figure 1), which is located in the central portion of the Ad-Dakhliyah alluvial plain (Figure 2). Lithic artefacts were initially observed eroding from the slope's surface, immediately downslope from a pile of massive dolomite boulders. Subsequent test pitting produced, buried *in situ*, artefacts that warranted a full-scale investigation.

A block of 20 m² was excavated in 1-m horizontal units just below the dolomite boulder and a 4-m² test block was placed some 10 m downslope from the main excavation area (Figure 3). All sediments were sieved through 5 mm mesh and every artefact over 2 cm was piece plotted. Layers were separated into natural units. The sequence was excavated in geological layers to a depth of approximately 1 m, from stratigraphic Unit A through stratigraphic Unit E.

Three discrete archaeological phases were recognized within these sediments. The two lower layers belong within the aceramic Neolithic (Early and Middle Holocene), while the uppermost stratum contained a shell bead that was dated to the late 4th/early 3rd millennium BC. Given the make-up of the lithic toolkit, as well as its position on the landscape, speculation is that the site functioned as a specialized hunting camp. In addition, there are high-quality halite (rock salt) deposits within the Qarat Al-Kibrit salt dome which it is likely that the inhabitants of QK1 were exploiting.

GEOGRAPHY AND GEOLOGY

The Ad-Dakhliyah region comprises a vast plain representing the southern edge of the Oman mountain piedmont. The plain is interlaced with a dense network of seasonally active wadian weakly dipping southwards into the Ḥaushi-Ḥuqf Depression. The landscape displays little relief, declining from 230 m in the north to approximately 100 m in the south

FIGURE 1. Aerial view of the Qarat Al-Kibrit salt dome, facing east (photo courtesy of Y. Guichard).

FIGURE 2. Map of the Sultanate of Oman showing the location of Qarat Al-Kibrit.

(Rogers *et al.* 1992). Between the villages of Adam and Haima, the plain is pockmarked by several diapiers (salt structures) that reach up to 50 m over the surrounding terrain and provide the only vertical relief on an otherwise flat bajada surface. These halokinetic structures, numbering about twenty, are formed as a result of the underlying Ghaba Salt Basin, a

fetid limestone and laminated black shale (Rogers *et al.* 1992). The structure is approximately 1 km in diameter and circular in shape. Quaternary sediments are found along the interior slope of the dome, perched about 5 m above the bajada surface.

phenomenon that is common in sedimentary basins with thick salt sequences (*ibid.*). The difference in buoyancy between salt and surrounding geologic beds creates landscape deformation brought on by tectonic events (Loosveld *et al.* 1996).

During the 2004 COPR campaign, a number of archaeological sites were documented within the halokinetic structures (Rose 2006) on low terraces throughout the alluvial plain and associated with wadian draining into the Haushi-Huqf Depression. One such diapir, Qarat Al-Kibrit, proved particularly rich in archaeological findspots. Qarat Al-Kibrit is an active salt dome that began forming in the late Tertiary and currently serves as the only vertical relief on the immediate landscape (Figure 4). The dome was created by downbuilding, which is the accumulation of sediments around a salt dome with the top of the dome remaining at or near the surface. The core comprises a disturbed mixture of halite, sulphate

FIGURE 3. *QK1* excavation units downslope from the dolomite blocks.

FIGURE 4. *Qarat Al-Kibrit salt dome from a distance, looking north.*

FIGURE 5. *Schematic of the local geomorphology around QK1, facing west. Drawing is not to scale.*

The archaeological material is located within these uplifted Quaternary sediments, a few meters below a gypsum crest that divides the endorheic basin of the salt dome from the outer alluvial system (Figure 5). The site is situated beneath massive dolomite blocks that were isolated by selective erosion from the surrounding gypsum-anhydrite rock. Localized drainage gullies incise the surface of the Quaternary sediments, their path controlled by flow around the dolomite boulders.

Five natural units, labeled A through E, are recognized within the excavated sediments (Figure 6). They are characterized as follows:

Unit A.

A tabular layer of surface material up to 10 cm thick. The matrix consists of weakly silty (very fine and fine) sand, an abundance of heterometric stones (maximum dimension of about 10 cm) formed of angular dolomite and rounded/sub-rounded anhydrite fragments. The rocky inclusions have a random orientation and distribution pattern. The sediment color (dry) is described as 10YR 7/2, or light grey. Phase I artefacts were collected from these loose sandy sediments.

FIGURE 6. Northwest section at QK1. Natural stratigraphic units A through E are depicted within the ~1 m section, although the base of Unit E has not yet been reached. Dashed line beneath Unit B denotes a geological unconformity.

Unit B.

Unit A grades into Unit B, becoming weakly cemented by gypsum. The matrix is silty (very fine and fine) sand, with a decreasing density of dolomite and anhydrite fragments towards the bottom of the layer. The stratum, ranging from 10 cm to 20 cm in thickness, is moderately compacted with a weakly visible sub-horizontal lamination dipping westwards. The color (dry) is similar to Unit A, described as 10YR 7/1, or light grey. When moist, the sediments are 9YR 5/4. There is a sharp linear lower boundary that slopes southwards. Phase I archaeological materials continue into this stratum, although in extremely low density within the bottom portion of the unit.

Unit C.

The matrix of Unit C comprises silty (very fine and fine) sand, ranging from moderately to highly cemented. Stones are scarce in this layer, though quite large, reaching a maximum dimension of 20 cm. Unit C ranges in thickness from 15 cm to 30 cm. It is 8YR 5/5 when moist. The lower boundary

grades into Unit D, marked by the distinct rocky inclusions that characterize the underlying stratum. Phase II chipped stone debris is dispersed randomly throughout this level, with a slightly higher concentration at the bottom, just above Unit D.

Unit D.

This layer is generally thin, between 5 cm and 10 cm thick. The matrix is silty (very fine and fine) sand mixed with an abundance of small angular pebbles of black dolomite that are between 1 cm and 5 cm in maximum dimension. Large anhydrite stones are also prevalent. Sediments within Unit D vary between unconsolidated to highly cemented; there is a clear lower boundary with Unit E, which abruptly becomes unconsolidated and has a much lower density of rocky inclusions. The Phase III assemblage was recovered almost exclusively from the base of Unit D. Given the high percentage of flat-lying artefacts, lithic refits and frequency of yellow radiolarite raw material (unique to Phase III), there appears to have been minimal post-depositional vertical move-

ment of this assemblage. It should be noted, however, that the slope of Unit D was somewhat steeper than previous strata and appears to be non-existent towards the eastern extent of the main excavation block; thus, it is likely the artefacts have undergone some degree of movement downslope.

Unit E.

Unit E has a very low density of rocky inclusions; the sediments are unconsolidated, well-sorted fine sands. The lower boundary of this stratum was not reached; it is greater than 50 cm thick. No artefacts were found.

Unit A represents the present-day, disturbed and trampled surface, partially derived from, and resting conformably on top of, Unit B. Units B and C are formed predominantly of aeolian input mixed with slope waste material formed of elements originating in the local pre-Quaternary bedrock. The sharp linear boundary between B and C, marked by significant differences in cementation and alternate angles of dipping, suggests the top of Unit C was exposed, cemented in gypsum and truncated prior to the deposition of Unit B. The high concentration of dolomitic clast in Unit D indicates a high-energy environment, probably a brief wet phase (or event) that caused increased erosion of the pre-Quaternary bedrock and subsequent run-off and deposition of slope waste. Conversely, the thick deposit of well-sorted, homogeneous sand in Unit E was likely laid down during a prolonged arid phase.

Post-depositional modifications of the sediments include moderate compaction and cementation. The sequence represents a poorly developed soil profile articulated in the A (Unit B) and C (Unit C) horizons, the latter being a weak gypsic horizon. Additionally, there is considerable bioturbation of the sediments in the form of vertical fissures that run through the entire sequence, caused by halokinetic uplift. The depositional processes observed at QK1 belong to a former cycle of landscape formation, most likely during the Holocene climatic optimum between roughly 10,000 and 6,000 years ago. This determination is based on direct dating of a perforated shell in Phase I and lithic techno-typological correlates found elsewhere in southeastern Arabia.

LITHIC ASSEMBLAGE

The lithic assemblage from QK1 was divided into three phases based on the material's stratigraphic position and distinct techno-typological features. These divisions are corroborated by artefact conjoins made within layers but not between them, as well as by related raw material within each layer that indicates they were knapped from the same cores. The total recovered lithic assemblage, organized by artefact class and archaeological level, is presented in Table 1.

Phase I

Phase I material was recovered from the surface and within a thick carpet of unconsolidated/semi-cemented sediments reaching a depth of approximately 20 cm; consequently, the assemblage is not necessarily associated with a single period of occupation. There is a noticeably higher distribution of artefacts downslope from the dolomite block (Figure 7). Presumably, this is because water draining into the dome was redirected by the boulder, thereby preventing the lithic material from being washed away. Additionally, human activity at the site may be associated with the presence of the dolomite block itself (e.g. protection from wind and sun, as well as concealment for hunting), although there is no direct evidence for this.

While the location of QK1 suggests it may have served as a base camp, the ratio of pieces with 1-50% cortex on the dorsal surface versus pieces with 51-100% cortex is 1.2, which indicates there was a relatively high percentage of cortical pieces. This is corroborated by the composition of artefact classes shown in Table 1, which shows a relatively large amount of debitage and debris but a low percentage of tools. So, while the site may have served multiple functions, one of them seems to have been early-stage manufacture of lithic artefacts.

Most of the artefacts (n=335, 79.2%) from the Phase I assemblage are derived from reddish-coloured, fine-grained radiolarite pebbles that are ubiquitous throughout the alluvial gravels surrounding the salt dome (Figure 8). This is followed by an extremely fine-grained yellow radiolarite that is derived from the same source (n=47, 11%), distinguished by

TABLE 1. Total lithic assemblage recovered from QK1, arranged by archaeological level and artefact class.

FIGURE 7. Vertical distribution of artefacts. Level 1 (Phase I) corresponds with Units A and B in Figure 6; Level 2 (Phase II) artefacts are found within Unit C; Level 3 (Phase III) artefacts are found at the base of Unit D.

FIGURE 8. *Radiolarite nodules outcropping from a gypsum crust on a terrace outside the salt dome.*

its excellent quality and different colour. Workable limestone, occurring within the dome, comprises thirty-one pieces (7.3%) of the assemblage. There are trace amounts of quartzite ($n=6$, 1.4%) and a white chert ($n=5$, 1.2%), both from unknown, non-local sources. The closest outcrop of quartzite is al-Jebel al-Aḥḍar, approximately 150 km to the north.

The aforementioned low cortex percentage ratio of Phase I is indicative of the site's proximity to radiolarite gravels just outside the salt dome, which provided the predominant source of raw material for the Phase I toolmakers. It is also noteworthy that non-local raw materials are somewhat more frequent in Phase I than in the underlying Phases II and III.

DEBITAGE AND CORES. The Phase I assemblage comprises 424 pieces, of which 184 are debitage and fifteen are cores, while the remaining artefacts are tools and debris. The reduction strategy can generally be described as a crude, single-platform blade technology. Twelve of the cores are flake-blade/let, two are flake cores and one is a

blade core. Twelve are single platform cores that exhibit unidirectional-parallel scar patterns on one or more working surfaces and the remaining three are opposed platform (Figure 9: b). Most of the cores ($n=12$) have some degree of edge grinding at the intersection of the dorsal face and striking platform.

Among the identifiable blanks (Table 2), blades and bladelets number fifty-four pieces comprising 27.3% of the blanks from Phase I (Figure 9: e, g-k), which is relatively prominent. There are five core trimming elements, four of which are core tablets (Figure 9: d), indicating this method was used for rejuvenating striking platforms. Six blanks are *éclats de taille*, although no actual bifacial tools were found in the Phase I assemblage. It is possible that the presence of these pieces is either the result of some form of turbation that brought artefacts up from underlying layers, or those bifacial tools manufactured or resharpened at the site being carried away.

Approximately 40% of the blanks exhibit some degree of edge grinding (Figure 9: g, k) and nearly 75% have lipping along the bulb of percussion. Fur-

FIGURE 9. *Lithic artefacts from QK1, Phase I; cores (a – c), core tablet (d), blade blanks (e, g, j, k), composite tool (f), perforator (h), and atypical sidescraper (i). Three-quarter scale.*

TABLE 2. Identifiable blank types from QK1 including both unmodified debitage and retouched tools, arranged by archaeological level and blank class.

thermore, bulbs tend to be diminutive morphological features suggesting that most of the flaking was carried out by soft-hammer percussion. Regarding platform morphology, 44.7% are straight, 31.9% are cortical straight/curved and only 8.1% are dihedral or faceted (the remaining 15.2% are either crushed or missing). Dorsal scar patterns reflect those of the cores: the most frequent type is unidirectional (47.1%), followed by unidirectional-parallel (24.7%), unidirectional-crossed (12.9%), convergent (9.4%), lateral-crested (2.4%), natural-crested (1.8%) and radial (1.2%). While there are three bidirectional cores, none of the blanks exhibits evidence for bidirectional flaking.

TOOLS. There are just seven tools in the Phase I toolkit. Figure 9: f depicts a unifacially retouched composite tool made on a flake combining burin, sidescraper and double-notch. Figure 9: h is an awl made on a cortical blade with steep obverse retouch, and Figure 9: i is an atypical sidescraper with semi-abrupt retouch made on a blade. In addition, there

was an atypical endscraper on a flake, a notch and double notch on a flake and cortical flake respectively, and a burin made on a blade. The burin had three spalls struck off. The first was a flake removed from the platform onto the ventral face, followed by a blow from the proximal end down the lateral edge and a final blow across the platform - these three removals intersect to form a single burin edge. Although there are only seven tools, the fact that over half of them were manufactured on blades supports the assertion that the production of blade-proportionate blanks was the primary reduction strategy at the site.

Among the artefacts recovered from the Phase I assemblage was a perforated shell bead (Figure 10) manufactured from the apex of a *Conus* sp. shell (Mienis, pers. Comm.). The shell was discovered near the top of geological Unit B in lightly cemented sands. AMS measurements carried out on the shell yielded an uncalibrated age of $4,852 \pm 41$ BP (Wk-15695), which was then calibrated with OxCal version 3.9 using the 1998 marine calibration curve

FIGURE 10. *Perforated bead made on the apex of a Conus shell.*

(Stuiver *et al.* 1998; Bronk Ramsey 2003). An additional computation was made to correct for the reservoir effect on marine shell ($\Delta R=207 \pm 30$), producing a final calculation of $2,945 \pm 250$ cal BC. Given its stratigraphic position, this age is considered the *terminus ante quem* for the Phase I assemblage.

Conus sp. are marine gastropods, for which the nearest sources are the Gulf of Oman or Arabian Sea coastlines, both approximately 150 km away. The manufacture of shell beads, particularly using *Conus* sp., is a common feature on coastal sites in Arabia throughout the Bronze Age (e.g. Barker 2003; Tosi and Usai 2003; Uerpmann and Uerpmann 2003). At Ra's Al-Junayz 1, situated on the northeastern coast of Oman, a Late Bronze Age structure was excavated that has been interpreted as a specialized workshop area for the manufacture of shell jewellery (Biagi *et al.* 1989). A similar specialized shell workshop area was also excavated from the nearby site of Ra's Al-Junayz 37 (Charpentier 1991), leading scholars to posit the existence of a regional interaction sphere. In this context, the presence of a marine shell bead at Qarat Al-Kibrit, Phase I, suggests that either the

inhabitants' mobility strategy included the littoral zone or else there was some degree of exchange with coastal populations. If the latter is the case, it is possible that the exploitation of halite (the only known resource within the crater) was associated with a Bronze Age interaction sphere linking the coast and hinterlands. Even today, rock salt extracted from the cavities inside Qarat Al-Kibrit is prized among Omanis for its purity (Figure 11); local oral tradition suggests that the crater has for millennia been a source of high-quality halite crystals valued for medicinal purposes (Al-Mahrooqi, pers. comm.).

Phase II

Phase II material occurs exclusively within geological Unit C and comprises fewer artefacts than the overlying assemblage. In fact, artefact distribution appears to be one dense scatter concentrated around square D12 (Figure 12). Like Phase I, most of the material is concentrated immediately downslope from the dolomite boulder.

By far the most frequent raw material is red radiolarite ($n=298$, 93.5%), followed by scarce amounts

FIGURE 11. Halite mining inside one of the cavities within Qarat Al-Kibrit.

FIGURE 12. Horizontal distribution of artefacts from QK1, Phase II. Three-quarter scale.

FIGURE 13. *Refit multiple platform core with alternating platform reduction strategy from QK1, Phase II. Three-quarter scale.*

of limestone (n=9, 2.8%), yellow radiolarite (n=6, 2.2%), white chert (n=3, 0.9%) and quartzite (n=2, 0.6%). Raw material procurement was much more localized than in Phase I, corresponding to a fundamentally different reduction strategy during this period. As was the case in Phase I, the 1-50:51-100 cortex percentage ratio is quite low (0.9), again suggesting that early stages of decortification were carried out on site. Also, similar to Phase I, tools make up a miniscule portion of the overall assemblage, comprising just five implements.

DEBITAGE AND CORES. There were 119 pieces of debitage and six cores in this assemblage. All six cores exclusively exhibit flake scars (in contrast to Phase I), primarily with unidirectional and unidirectional-crossed scar patterns. One of the cores has multiple platforms and alternating scar patterns, seemingly an *ad hoc* prismatic approach to the core's volume. Figure 13 depicts this specimen with several refit flakes, illustrating the haphazard reduction strategy employed by the Phase II toolmakers. Two of the specimens are cores-on-flakes, following the broad definition of this category suggested by Usik

(2001). One such core-on-flake from this assemblage was almost completely refit, revealing a multiple platform alternating reduction strategy (Figure 14).

The percentage of blade-proportionate blanks is dramatically less than in the overlying stratum (down from 27.3% to 5.1%), another indication of the different reduction strategies practiced in Phase II. There are ten *éclats de taille*¹ (Figure 15: a), although the raw material does not match that of the bifacial point fragment also found within the Phase II assemblage. Scar patterns show a significantly decreased percentage of unidirectional-parallel types (12.8%), with far more unidirectional and unidirectional-crossed (48.6% and 19.3% respectively). There were five lateral-crested pieces (4.6%), in which scars are positioned along the ridge of a *débordant* blank, directed inwards toward the middle of the piece. Although these pieces were not classified as typical core trimming elements, they suggest either platform maintenance to rejuvenate a striking platform or reformation of the convexity around the working surface.

Approximately a quarter of the blanks have edge grinding (n=27) and two-thirds are lipped (n=73).

FIGURE 14. *Refit core-on-flake from QK1, Phase II. Three-quarter scale.*

FIGURE 15. *Lithic artefacts from QK1, Phase II; biface thinning flake (a), denticulate (b), atypical endscraper (c), distal point fragment (d). Three-quarter scale.*

Most of the striking platforms are straight (n=52, 39.7%), cortical-straight (n=34, 26.0%) or cortical-curved (n=9, 6.9%). There are very few dihedral (n=9, 6.9%) or faceted (n=6, 4.6%), which would indicate platform shaping. It is interesting to note that the percentage of mistakes, expressed by hinge/step/overpassed distal terminations, is quite pronounced in Phase II at 28.2%. This is further indication of the haphazard, *ad hoc* core reduction strategy.

TOOLS. There were three unifacial and two bifacial tools in the Phase II assemblage. The unifacial tools consist of an atypical endscraper on a primary flake (Figure 15: c), a denticulate (Figure 15: b) and a retouched flake with obverse, marginal retouch. Both bifacial tools are diagnostic of the Arabian Bifacial Tradition (ABT). One is the distal fragment of a bifacial point (possibly lanceolate). The piece was made from red radiolarite and exhibits thinning via both soft-hammer percussion as well as very fine pressure flaking at the distal extremity (Figure 15: d). Although broken, the shape and mode of retouch on the bifacial point classifies it as a Type 4 point in Edens' (1982) Neolithic typology. The second bifacial piece is a 'bifacial tile', a tool form initially documented by Kapel (1967) during the Danish Expedition to Qatar. The specimen is made on a large slab of dolomite limestone that outcrops within the salt dome. The piece is flat, about 1.3 cm in thickness, nearly 25 cm long and 12 cm at its widest point. The tool has an elongated triangular shape and is biconvex in cross-section. Retouch consists of semi-steep bifacial

scraper retouch along the entire distal margin, forming a convex working edge. According to the work of the Danish Expedition, these tools (as well as the Type 4 bifacial point) are diagnostic of the ABT, suggesting a correlation of the Phase II assemblage with the Middle Holocene climatic optimum between approximately 8,000 and 6,000 years ago.

Phase III

Phase III is the lowest archaeological stratum at Qarat Al-Kibrit. The material occurs within Unit D, a thin layer of cemented dolomite gravels indicative of an intense, short-term episode of increased rainfall. Like both overlying phases, the artefacts are primarily distributed within a small, conscripted scatter downslope from the dolomite boulder (Figure 16). The assemblage comprises 246 pieces, of which 35% are cores, tools and debitage, and the remaining 65% are debris. Of the 159 chips, thirty-two can be classified as *éclats de taille*, presumably a byproduct of pressure flaking (Figure 17: a-b). This is not surprising given the presence of a pressure-flaked bifacial point found in this stratum, described below in detail.

Yellow radiolarite is significantly more prevalent than in the previous phases, comprising 105 pieces, about 43% of the assemblage; red radiolarite is still the most prominent, totalling 137 (55.5%), followed by a trace amount of limestone (n=4, 1.6%). While the red and yellow radiolarite pebbles appear to grade into one another in a single continuum, the yellow material tends to be extremely fine grained

FIGURE 16. *Horizontal distribution of artefacts from QK1, Phase III.*

and virtually free of inclusions, a much higher quality raw material. Because of the specialized bifacial reduction strategy apparent in Phase III, it is possible the flintknappers deliberately chose better raw materials than the somewhat crude *ad hoc* reduction strategies seen in Phases I and II.

Similar to both of the preceding phases, the 1-50:51-100 cortex percentage ratio is extremely low at 1.2. So, while the reduction strategies may be different, the raw material procurement strategy appears to remain the same throughout the entire sequence. Phase III toolmakers obtained nearby radiolarite cobbles from the surrounding alluvial plain, subsequently carrying out early stages of decortification at the site.

DEBITAGES AND CORES. The Phase III assemblage is dominated by *façonnage* technology; there is almost no evidence for core reduction. Two ambiguous pieces were collected that demonstrated bilateral/radial convexity maintenance on both faces and some degree of preparation along the primary

striking platform. One such specimen is illustrated in Figure 18, showing radial flaking on one face and bilateral thinning on the opposed face (with lateral refit). The final removal was initially interpreted as an overpassed Levallois flake; however, in light of the radiocarbon date from Phase I, presumably Holocene span for the entire stratigraphic sequence, and associated techno-typological features in the Phase III assemblage, the specimens are considered early stage preforms rather than cores. It appears the overpassed longitudinal blow removed far too much of the preform and so the piece was discarded.

Among the debitage, blades are virtually nonexistent (n=1, 1.3%), while *éclats de taille* comprise a third of all pieces (n=26, 33.3%). This is not surprising given the number of preforms. At 75.4% (n=52), the Phase III assemblage has the highest incidence of lipping of all three phases. Edge preparation, as well, is relatively frequent on 38.4% (n=27) of blanks.

The prevalence of *façonnage* reduction is exhibited in both striking platform morphology and dorsal scars, where radial scar patterns jump to 34.6%

FIGURE 17. *Lithic artefacts from QKI, Phase III; biface thinning chips (a, b), biface thinning flakes (c-f), bifacial preforms (g-h), medial point fragment (i). Three-quarter scale.*

(n=28). Unmodified straight (n=19, 21.3%), cortical straight (n=10, 11.2%) or cortical curved platforms (n=6, 6.7%) are far less frequent than the preceding phases, accounting for less than half the blanks in this assemblage, while dihedral and faceted forms increase to 38.3% (n=34).

TOOLS. The Phase III toolkit is heavily bifacial. There were seven preforms (including the two aforementioned specimens). Most are from early stages of reduction and all are on relatively flat radiolarite plaquettes. Figure 17: g depicts a very early stage preform, in which only a few exploratory blows

FIGURE 18. *Refit bifacial preform from QK1, Phase III. Three-quarter scale.*

were carried out before snapping the piece, while Figure 17: h shows a specimen that is somewhat further along in reduction, both sides having undergone some degree of thinning.

The only completed tool was recovered on the very last day in the field, while taking sediment sam-

ples for optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating. The piece is a medial fragment of a pressure-flaked, bifacial pedunculate, falling into Type 1 of Edens' (1982) typological scheme (Figure 17: i). The piece is extremely well made, with parallel ribbon-flaking on both faces, forming a lenticular

cross-section. While the proximal and distal ends are snapped off, enough of the butt remains to indicate the piece was shouldered. The form and quality of pressure flaking are both indicative of the Middle Holocene ABT. The point is made on yellow radiolarite, although seemingly from a slightly different source than the associated Phase III debitage.

Considering these techno-typological characteristics, this archaeological phase is interpreted as an ephemeral hunting camp. There is no other reduction strategy besides the *façonnage* production of points; therefore, the evidence suggests a fairly limited range of activities carried out on site. Based on the geomorphology of Unit D, which suggests short-term, intense rainfall, it is possible that hunters were drawn to the salt dome because of water pooling inside or to hunt animals that were attracted to the salt deposits (if not to the salt deposits themselves).

DISCUSSION

The archaeological site of Qarat Al-Kibrit 1 is, to date, the only stratified Neolithic site in the interior of Oman. As such, QK1 provides a unique opportunity to examine Early/Middle Holocene human habitation in the Ad-Dakhliyah region of the Sultanate. Taking into account the radiocarbon date from the top of Unit B, typologically diagnostic characteristics of bifacial tools from Units C and D, and stratigraphic correlation with the palaeoenvironmental framework for the region (Parker *et al.* 2006), we propose that the three archaeological phases documented at QK1 span from the 6th to the 3rd millennia BC.

There is little doubt as to why the locality at QK1 was chosen for habitation. There were abundant resources immediately available, including radiolarite nodules on the surrounding alluvial plain, high-quality salt crystal inside the salt dome and, given the timeframe within the climatic optimum, freshwater draining into the basin. The position of QK1 on the rim of the salt dome would have been ideal for hunting game moving across the landscape. In addition the massive dolomite boulder provided adequate concealment as well as shelter from the elements. The boulder shielded not only the ancient inhabit-

ants at QK1 but also protected the artefacts and sediments from being eroded downslope and was, thus, instrumental in post-depositional preservation of the archaeological sequence.

Phase III, the earliest period of occupation at QK1, was excavated within Unit D, a silty-sandy matrix mixed with small angular pebbles that indicate a semi-humid climatic regime. The assemblage is characterized almost exclusively by bifacial reduction, with preforms and thinning flakes comprising a high percentage of the debitage. This phase also yielded the medial fragment of a Type 1 Neolithic arrowhead made by very fine pressure flaking, known from several dated Middle Holocene contexts throughout Southeastern Arabia (Charpentier 2008). The ensuing cultural horizon, Phase II, was difficult to discern within the stratigraphic sequence. It was found in geologic Unit C, which conformably overlies Unit D; the stratum was only distinguishable based on the absence of small pebbles. Given these features, we surmise that the landscape was becoming increasingly arid and that there was no longer sufficient run-off to mobilize pebble-sized clasts. The corresponding lithic assemblage in Phase II yielded *ad hoc* cores and the distal fragment of a Neolithic Type 4 lanceolate-shaped arrowhead. Considering their stratigraphic positions and related typological features (i.e. pressure-flaked points), Phase III and Phase II appear to be related and may be attributed to repeated ephemeral occupations by the same or similar groups.

Phase I stands out in stark contrast, both technologically and stratigraphically, from the underlying horizons. Artefacts from the uppermost strata were recovered from Unit A and Unit B, which uncomfortably rest atop Unit C. These moderately compacted sediments are weakly cemented in gypsum, suggesting the onset of arid conditions. This is corroborated by the marine shell dated to $2,945 \pm 250$ cal BC, placing it in a semi-arid phase after the climatic optimum (Parker *et al.* 2006). The lithic assemblage from QK1, Phase I, bears no resemblance to either of the underlying assemblages from Phase II or Phase III. There are no bifacial elements; rather, the predominant reduction strategy was the manufacture of simple unidirectional blades from single-

platform volumetric cores. We posit that the Phase I occupants at QK1 were exploiting halite deposits within the dome. The presence of a marine shell bead suggests their interaction sphere involved a system of exchange with settlements along the coast. Alternatively, Phase I occupants may have practiced seasonal transhumance between the coast and hinterlands.

QK1 is not an isolated findspot; during the 2004 campaign, the COPR project documented a number of lithic scatters throughout the salt domes and low terraces that interlace Ad-Dakhliyah south of Adam. In light of these findings, we recommend continued exploration of the numerous diapirs situated on the Ad-Dakhliyah alluvial plain to further articulate prehistoric occupation of this region.

NOTES

¹ This category refers to a specific blank type that is indicative of bifacial shaping, thereby suggesting the production of bifacial implements on site.

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Jeffrey I. Rose, Oxford Brookes University, Oxford, UK

Vitaly I. Usik, Ukraine National Academy of Science, Kiev, Ukraine

Diego E. Angelucci, University of Trento, Trento, Italy

Ali Al-Mahrooqi, Ministry of Heritage and Culture, Muscat, Oman

